

Population Changes in Lower Myanmar (1852-1941); A Demographic Profile

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Abstract

The British administration produced population returns that were published in the annual reports from 1852 onwards. The introduction of censuses by the British makes it possible to trace the history of population growth during the colonial period with some assurance. The first modern census was taken in 1872 and followed by a second in 1881. Thereafter decennial censuses were taken regularly until 1941. The population of Lower Myanmar rose from 2,747,148 in 1872 to 8,917,733 in 1941. This growth of population was influenced by the components of population changes; migration movements and natural increase. This growth of population during the pre-war period was mainly because of increase in natural growth, increasing efficiency of enumeration and the influx of non-indigenous population.

Keywords: Censuses, Lower Myanmar, Migration, Natural Increase, Urbanization

Introduction

This paper deals mainly with the population changes in Lower Myanmar (1852-1941) and its impact on society. The population of Myanmar grew very gradually from the sixteenth century onwards. The population of Myanmar under Myanmar Kings about 1800 has been subjected to varying estimates. Many of the early European visitors and emissaries to the Myanmar court had made estimates of the population numbers between 1800 and 1860. The size of the population of early Konbaung state was subjected to various estimates done by the British visitors. But no one made estimates for separate figures of Lower Myanmar population. As the population of Lower Myanmar around 1800 was only one quarter of the total population estimated by Tun Wai, Lower Myanmar, at the time of British annexation after the Second Anglo-Myanmar War in 1852 was therefore sparsely populated and underdeveloped. The Lower Myanmar population however trebled during the 70 years period between 1872 and 1941. With the growth of population, the socio-economic conditions of Lower Myanmar also increased, especially the agro-based economy.

Structure of the Paper

Lower Myanmar, at the time of British annexation after the Second Anglo-Myanmar war in 1852 was sparsely populated and under-developed. The British administration produced population returns that were published in the annual reports from 1852 onwards. But there are major problems with the use of these figures as demographic data. The two factors that mitigated against the use of this data are that the figures applied to Bago and Mottama only and excluded the population of Rakhine, Taninthayi and also that the data was produced for the British administration by the village headmen for capitation tax collections. The local village headmen routinely under-reported the number of tax payers in their circles. This not only protected the people from the capitation tax but also provided the headman with an income in the form of bribery and gifts.¹ The administration itself admitted considerable under-enumeration which is hardly surprising, but is discouraging to a demographer. However, the

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¹ (a) Judith. L. Richell, *Disease and Demography in Colonial Burma*, Singapore, NUS Press, 2006, pp. 10-14 (Hereafter cited as Judith Richell; *Disease and Demography*)

(b) *A Study of the Social and Economic History of Burma (British-Burma), part (III), British-Burma before the Opening of the Suez Canal 1861-62=1867-1868*, Rangoon, Economic and Social Board, pp. 4-6 (Hereafter

population of Lower Myanmar at the time of British annexation in 1852 can be estimated at 1.43 million, which was calculated based on the capitation tax returns and average density was only 19 persons per square mile.¹

In the earlier years of British rule, when the condition of the area was still unsettled, the capitation tax returns must have been much less accurate. Besides, it can be made an approximate of population of Myanmar around 1852 in the following way. Dr. B.N. Kaul has estimated that the total population of Lower Myanmar in 1856 was 1,461,000.²

Comparing it with the estimates of population of Lower Myanmar for the year 1800, it can be seen that it had increased by 19.4 percent in the space of about fifty years. The tax returns referred to were population figures contained in the annual reports, published by the British administration from 1852. The following table shows the extracts from the reports for selected years.

Table (1) Lower Myanmar; Selected Population Returns³

Date	Population Numbers
1852	718,000
1859	948,731
1864	1,350,989

The Annual Report of 1864-65 stated that the recorded population increased from 948, 731 in 1859 to 1,350,989 in 1864 was mainly due to the increased accuracy of the returns.⁴ The earliest population figures for British-Burma as a whole are those of 1861, which gave a population of 1.9 million.⁵ When the Maritime Provinces were amalgamated into British-Burma in 1862, the population of Lower Myanmar rose to 2.021 million (2,020,634) and the density of population was 27 persons per-square mile. The returns shows an increase from 2.021 million in 1862 to 2.50 million (2,491,736) in 1870. The population returns for 1870 gave 2,491,736 which show an increase of 70,587 in 1871 or 2.83 percent.⁶ These figures shows an increase of 541, 689 or within a fraction of 26.8 percent on the population during ten years (1862-1871). It also gives the earlier estimates for comparison with the corrected 1872 census figures. It will be noted that the census returns give an increase over the previous year's population returns of 184,825 or 7.21 percent. When the first regular census in British-Burma was taken in 1872, the population was given as 2.75 million (2,747,148).⁷ During the colonial period, the first modern census was taken in 1872 and followed by a second in 1881. Thereafter decennial censuses were taken regularly until 1941.⁸

¹ J.S. Furnivall, *An Introduction to the Political Economy of Burma*, Rangoon, Burmese Advertising Press, 1957, p. 245 (Hereafter cited as Furnivall, *Political Economy*)

² J.S. Furnivall, *An Introduction to the Political Economy of Burma*, Rangoon, Burmese Advertising Press, 1957, p. 245 (Hereafter cited as Furnivall, *Political Economy*)

³ (a) Furnivall, *Colonial Policy and Practice*, p. 59.

(b) *Economic and Social History*, pp. 6-7.

⁴ (a) *Report on the Administration of the Province of British-Burma for the Year 1864-65*, Calcutta, Military Orphan Press, 1866, p. 41

(b) *Economic and Social History*, pp. 6-7.

⁵ Furnivall, *Colonial Policy and Practice*, p. 59

⁶ *Report on the Census of British-Burma, 1872*, Rangoon, Government Press, 1875, p. 6 (Hereafter cited as *Census of British-Burma, 1872*)

⁷ *Census of British-Burma, 1872*, p. 6

⁸ (a) *Burma Handbook*, Simla, Government of India Press, 1944, p. 10. (Hereafter cited as *Burma Handbook*)

(b) M. Ismael Khin Maung, *The Population of Burma; An Analysis of the 1973 Census*, Papers of the East West Population Institute, Number 97, April, 1986 (Hereafter cited as M. Ismael Khin Maung, *An*

The most important sources for demographic data are census and vital registration records. Both of these sources were introduced by the British administration. As a province of India, Myanmar was included in the census of India up to and including 1931. In 1941, an independent census of Myanmar was held.¹ According to the last census enumerated in 1941, the population of Lower Myanmar in 1941 was found to be approximately 8.92 million (8,917,733).² A closer inspection of the census records reveals major difficulties with each individual census and their comparability with each other. The major problems identified for examination include the changing calendar dates of the census. The variations and fluctuations in the methods of enumeration used caused great difficulties—some were synchronous, some non-synchronous and in some areas, estimates were used.

The 1872 census was held on 15 August in the wet season and all the other censuses were taken in February and March. The dates on which the census enumerated were not constant but progressed from 17 February in 1881 to 18 March in 1921 and back to 24 February in 1931. The shift of census dates mentioned above, from 17 February in 1881 to 18 March in 1921, has a particular significance for the study of the demographic history of Myanmar. The success of the agricultural economy of Lower Myanmar depended to a large extent upon seasonal labours from Upper Myanmar and India. These migrant labours usually returned to their homes during February or March. The migration of the census dates also from February to March and back to February means that the number of workers (enumerated) in transit must also have varied from year to year.³ The British administration was again in difficulty in Lower Myanmar, this time in the districts of Hinthada and Tharyawaddy. In 1931, parts of these districts were subject to a non-synchronous census due to the Saya San rebellion. Other districts such as Bago, Pyapon, Insein, Pyay and Thayetmyo were also considerably disturbed, with a high probability that the accuracy of the census was damaged in those districts as well.⁴

The population totals by census, the dates on which the census was taken and the increase and percentage increase are shown in the following table.

Table (2) Censuses of Lower Myanmar (1872-1941)⁵

Date of Census	Population	Increase	Percent
15 August 1872	2,747,148	726,514	35.95
17 February 1881	3,736,771	989,623	36.02
26 February 1891	4,658,627	921,856	24.67
1 March 1901	5,580,158	921,531	19.78
10 March 1911	6,932,830	1,352,672	24.24
18 March 1921	7,047,706	114,876	1.66
26 February 1931	7,964,855	917,149	13.01
2 February 1941	8,917,733	952,878	11.96

¹ Judith Richell, *Disease and Demography*, pp. 17-18

² (a) *Burma Handbook*, p. 10

(b) M. Ismael Khin Maung, *An Analysis of the 1973 Census*

³ Judith Richell; *Disease and Demography*, pp. 28-29

⁴ Judith Richell, *Disease and Demography*, p. 27

⁵ (a) *Burma Handbook*, p.10.

(b) *Census of 1891, Imperial series, Volume IX, Burma Report, Vol. I*, (Rangoon, Superintendent Government Printing, Burma, 1892, p. 13 (Hereafter cited as *Census of 1891, Burma, Report*)

(c) *Census of India, 1931, Vol XI, Burma, Part I, Report*, Rangoon, Superintendent, Government Printing and Stationery, Burma, 1933, p. 8 (Hereafter cited as *Census of India, 1931, Burma, Report*)

(d) M. Ismael Khin Maung, *An Analysis of the 1973 Census*.

It will be noted that the decennial increase in population exceeded ten percent in every decade except 1911 to 1921. During the decade 1911-1921, when the population growth was affected by the world wide influenza epidemic, it appeared to have retarded the increase of population in Lower Myanmar. The small rate of increase of the population between 1911 and 1921 is mostly attributed to the influenza epidemic of 1918-1919. The 1921 census report estimated that the epidemic accounted for a fall of 2.85 percent of rate of increase of population.¹

The population of Lower Myanmar rose from 2,747,148, in 1872 to 8,917,733 in 1941. The Lower Myanmar population therefore trebled during the 70 years period between 1872 and 1941. The large increase in population between 1852 and 1941 was due not only to economic progress but also due to the fact that returns were getting more accurate. Moreover, there are three main reasons for this increase of population in Lower Myanmar and the resulting change in the distribution of population; Natural increase as a result of increasing prosperity, Immigration from Upper Myanmar and India and greater accuracy of counting in Lower Myanmar.² These factors mentioned caused the sparsely populated area of Lower Myanmar to the densely populated area and the growth of population. The census reports divided the whole of Lower Myanmar into two natural divisions, the delta and the coast to study the distribution of population. Roughly comparable sizes of the population in each of these divisions are given in the following table.

Table (4) Population of Each Division in Lower Myanmar³

Division	1901		1911		1921		1931	
	Actual	Density	Actual	Density	Actual	Density	Actual	Density
Delta	3,741,328	105	4,332,402	122	4,820,715	135	5,435,058	152
Coast	1,240,126	33	1,432,297	38	1,598,493	42	1,845,301	49

The table shows that the proportion of population in each division is roughly constant. The concentration of the population in the different division can be seen from the table showing the densities of population in different censuses. It can be seen that the delta division is more densely populated area in Lower Myanmar. Moreover, the very rapid development of the delta area caused a degree of administrative change and shifted boundaries and resigned district. The British administration divided Lower Myanmar into several districts for the administration. The populations of Lower Myanmar by district from contemporary census records are shown in the following table.

¹ (a) R.M. Sundrum, "Population Statistics of Burma", *Economic Research Project, Statistical Paper, No.3, December, 1957*, University of Rangoon, p. 12 (Hereafter cited as, Sundrum, *Population Statistics of Burma*)

(b) *Census of India, 1921, Vol. X, Burma, Part I, Report*, Rangoon, Superintendent, Government Printing, Burma, 1923, p. 34 (Hereafter cited as *Census of India, 1921, Burma, Report*)

² (a) *Report on the Census of British-Burma, 1881*, Rangoon, The Government Press, 1881, p. 22

(b) *Census of India, 1931, Burma, Report*, pp. 22

³ (a) *Census of India, 1921, Burma, Report*, p. 55
 (b) *Census of India, 1931, Burma, Report*, p. 38.
 (c) Sundrum, *Population Statistics of Burma*, 21

Table (5) Lower Myanmar; Numbers of Population by District from Contemporary Census Records¹

<i>District</i>	<i>1872</i>	<i>1881</i>	<i>1891</i>	<i>1901</i>	<i>1911</i>	<i>1921</i>	<i>1931</i>	<i>1941</i>
Sandoway	54,725	64,010	77,134	90,927	102,803	112,029	129,245	139,747
Rangoon district	332,324					* Became Hanthawaddy and Thongwa		
Rangoon town	98,745	134,176	180,324	234,881	293,316	341,962	400,415	500,800
Bassein	322,689	389,419	475,002	391,427	440,988	489,173	571,043	664,724
Myanaung	476,612					* Became Henzada and Tharrawaddy		
Prome	274,872	322,342	360,252	365,804	378,871	371,575	410,651	436,714
Thayetmyo	156,816	169,560	250,161			* Reunited with Upper Burma		
Moulmein town	46,472	53,107	*	*	*	*	*	*
Shwegyin	129,485	171,144	198,521			* Split up among Pegu, Thaton and Taungoo		
Toungoo	86,166	128,848	162,132	279,315		381,883	428,670	*
Hanthawaddy	*	427,720	267,039	484,811	539,109	304,624	408,831	459,422
Tharrawaddy	*	278,255	347,454	395,570	433,320	492,429	508,319	593,909
Thongwa	*	284,063	446,076	484,400		* Became Maubin, Pyapon and Myaungmya		
Henzada	*	318,077	380,927	484,558	532,357	550,920	613,280	693,271
Pegu	*	*	301,420	339,572	429,121	445,620	489,169	582,959
Myaungmya	*	*	*	303,274	334,852	370,551	444,784	488,031
Thaton	*	*	*	343,510	416,975	471,100	532,628	592,638
Maubin	*	*	*	*	305,073	330,106	371,509	428,092
Pyapon	*	*	*	*	256,215	288,994	334,158	385,008
Insein	*	*	*	*	*	293,083	331,452	387,345

Notes: *District not in existence at that date.

¹ (a) Judith. Richell, *Disease and Demography*, p.

(b) *Census of India, 1891-1931, Burma, Part II, Tables*, Table II, Variation in Population Since Last-census

As indicated in the table, the population of Lower Myanmar was unevenly distributed and topography is the main controlling factors for population distribution. The table reveals that most of the districts in Lower Myanmar are thinly populated. In contrast, the thinly populated districts are located all in the fertile lowlands of the river basins and the coastal strip. The population per-square mile in 1941 of the four divisions in Lower Myanmar and the most densely populated districts within each division are shown in the following table.

Table (6) Population densities in Divisions and in most densely populated districts in 1941
(Per-square mile) ¹

Division	Density	District	Density
Pegu	215	Hantharwaddy	238
Irrawaddy	198	Maubin	261
Arakan	74	Akyab	147
Tenansserim	56	Thaton	122

It will be noted in the table that there is a great difference between population density in a whole division and that in the most densely populated district within the division. Certain districts in the list above, notably Sittwe and Thaton contain thinly populated areas.

Turning to the rural and urban population, the figures for rural and urban population of each district in Lower Myanmar are given in the following table.

¹ J.Russell Andrus, *Burmese Economic Life*, London, Standford University Press, 1947, pp. 25-26 (Hereafter cited as Andrus, *Burmese Economic Life*)

Table (8) Lower Myanmar; Rural and Urban Population Distribution¹

District	1881			1891			1901			1911			1921			1931		
	Total	towns	villages	Total	towns	villages	Total	towns	villages	Total	towns	villages	Total	towns	villages	Total	towns	villages
Akyab				416,305	37,938	378,367	481,666	35,680	445,986	529,943	37,893	492,050	576,430	36,569	539,861	637,580	40,338	597,242
N.Araikan				14,628	-	14,628	20,682	-	20,682	22,234	-	22,234	-	-	-	-	-	-
Hill district of Arakan				-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20,914	-	20,914	21,418	-	21,418
Kyaukpyu				163,832	6,634	157,198	168,827	3,145	165,682	184,916	3,323	181,593	199,873	3,884	195,989	220,292	4,232	216,060
Sandoway				77,134	2,531	74,603	90,927	2,845	88,082	102,803	3,360	99,443	112,029	3,762	108,267	129,245	4,070	125,175
Rangoon city				180,324	180,324	-	234,881	234,881	-	293,316	293,316	-	341,962	341,962	-	400,415	400,415	-
Insein	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	293,083	14,308	278,775	331,452	51,857	279,595
Hanthawaddy				267,039	-	267,039	484,811	-	484,811	539,109	24,889	514,220	364,624	23,346	341,278	408,831	25,616	383,215
Pugu	-	-	-	301,420	10,762	290,658	339,572	14,132	325,440	429,121	17,104	412,017	445,620	26,265	419,355	489,969	40,699	449,270
Tharrawaddy				347,454	11,269	336,185	395,570	21,380	374,190	433,320	23,586	409,734	492,429	43,429	449,000	508,319	51,312	457,007
Prome				360,252	52,679	307,573	365,804	49,267	316,537	378,871	48,036	330,835	371,575	49,329	322,246	410,651	50,182	360,469
Thongwa				446,076	36,343	403,733	484,410	19,402	465,008	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bassein				475,002	44,328	430,674	391,427	39,046	352,481	440,988	49,692	391,296	489,473	56,224	433,249	571,043	56,908	514,135
Henzada				380,927	39,373	341,554	484,558	54,507	430,051	532,357	53,296	479,061	550,920	38,508	512,412	613,280	44,394	568,886
Myaungmya	-	-	-	-	-	-	303,274	9,721	293,553	334,852	13,592	321,260	370,551	20,842	349,709	444,784	24,879	419,905
Maubin	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	305,073	27,217	277,856	330,106	21,016	309,090	371,509	35,156	346,353
Pyapon	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	256,215	24,972	231,243	288,994	27,911	261,083	334,158	37,848	296,310
Thayetmyo				250,161	26,113	224,048	239,706	26,031	243,675	248,275	24,471	223,804	255,406	21,987	233,410	274,177	21,790	252,387
Amherst				417,312	68,565	348,747	300,173	62,365	237,808	367,918	57,582	310,336	417,910	67,888	350,022	516,233	72,081	444,152
Tavoy				94,921	15,099	79,822	109,979	22,371	87,608	135,293	25,074	110,219	156,786	27,480	129,306	179,964	29,018	150,946
Mergui				73,748	10,137	63,611	88,744	11,987	76,757	111,424	14,889	96,535	135,465	17,297	118,168	161,987	20,405	141,582
Taungoo				102,132	19,232	142,900	279,315	23,453	255,862	351,076	26,583	324,493	381,883	31,541	350,342	428,670	36,906	391,764
Salween				31,439	-	31,439	37,837	-	37,837	46,608	-	46,608	50,379	-	50,379	53,186	-	53,186
Thaton	-	-	-	-	-	-	343,510	20,979	322,531	416,975	20,519	396,456	471,100	22,159	448,841	532,628	23,462	509,166
Shwegyin				198,521	13,918	184,603	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

¹ Census of India, 1891-1931, Part II, Tables, Imperial Table I, Area, Houses and Population

This table shows that the rural population in every district is larger than that of urban population except Yangon city. A high percentage of Lower Myanmar population was in Yangon. Its special attraction as the main point of entry for immigrants was that it was not only the administrative capital but also the commercial and financial centre. The population of Yangon city has increased from 98,745 in 1872 to 501,219 in 1941, an increase of 407.59 percent in seventy years.¹

Regarding the rural-urban population, it can be studied by comparing the population and percent changes in population of Lower Myanmar and population of Yangon in the following table.

Table (9) Population and percent change in population of
Lower Myanmar and Yangon²

Decade	Population		Percent change	
	Lower Myanmar	Yangon	Lower Myanmar	Yangon
1872	2,747,148	98,745	35.95	
1872-1881	3,736,771	135,711	36.02	37.4
1881-1891	4,658,627	184,134	24.67	35.7
1891-1901	5,580,158	248,060	19.78	34.7
1901-1911	6,932,830	296,422	24.24	19.5
1911-1921	7,047,706	345,505	1.66	16.6
1921-1931	7,964,855	400,415	13.0	15.9
1931-1941	8,917,733	501,219	11.96	25.2

From the above table, it can be seen that in every decade since 1872, the population of Yangon has increased. Before 1900, the rate of growth was relatively constant for each decade and higher than the rates of growth between 1901 and 1941. During the decade 1901-1911, the rate of growth declined to some extent and continued to decline to a lesser extent in the following decades. In the decade 1931-1941, the rate of population growth was somewhat higher than in any of the previous three decades, probably owing in large part to the opening of the Burma Road which during the early phases of the Sino-Japanese War caused Yangon to be the port of entry for much of the goods going to China.³

Turning to the age and sex structure of population, the age and sex structure of population by the five year age groups for the census years is shown in the following tables.

¹ *Census of India, 1931, Burma, Report*, p. 48

² (a) Richard. W. Redick, *A Demographic and Ecological Study of Rangoon*, Chicago, Illinois, 1961, p. 19

(b) *Burma Handbook*, p. 10

(c) *Census of India, 1931, Burma, Report*, p. 8

(d) *Census of 1891, Burma, Report*, p. 13

³ M. Ismael Khin Maung, *An Analysis of the 1973 Census*, p. 8.

Table (10) Age distribution of 30,000 of each sex¹

Age group	1901				1911			
	Total	Male	Female	%	Total	Male	Female	%
0-5	8,707	4,075	4,632	14.51	8,390	3,953	4,435	14.88
5-10	7,578	3,647	3,931	12.63	7,930	3,811	4,127	13.22
10-15	6,302	3,163	3,139	10.50	6,511	3,273	3,238	10.85
15-20	5,644	2,586	3,058	9.41	5,493	2,562	2,931	9.16
20-40	20,434	10,607	9,827	34.06	20,228	10,372	9,856	33.71
40-60	8,670	4,598	4,072	14.45	8,795	4,678	4,117	14.66
60+	2,665	1,324	1,341	4.44	2,647	1,351	1,296	4.41

Age group	1921				1931			
	Total	Male	Female	%	Total	Male	Female	%
0-5	7,941	3,784	4,157	13.24	8,693	4,155	4,538	14.49
5-10	7,756	3,768	3,988	12.93	7,495	3,679	3,816	12.49
10-15	6,724	3,392	3,332	11.21	6,842	3,386	3,456	11.40
15-20	5,901	2,762	3,139	9.84	5,751	2,711	3,040	9.59
20-40	19,394	9,938	9,456	32.32	19,694	10,085	9,609	32.82
40-60	9,438	4,900	4,538	15.73	8,974	4,683	4,291	14.96
60+	2,846	1,456	1,390	4.74	2,551	1,301	1,250	4.25

The age and sex structure of population given in the above tables with a large preponderance of adult male reflected the character of population as an immigrant population. Lower Myanmar population is seen to be a relatively young population. With respect to the distribution of the sexes, males outnumber females in Lower Myanmar. According to this age structure, the imbalance in the proportions of dependents and productive persons caused a mismatch of income generation and income users, which in turn reduced savings and investments in such things as education, housing, social welfare and other social needs. The continued high proportion of young people will vitiate economic development and lower level of living. An examination of the historical pattern of sex composition in Lower Myanmar reveals the demographic impact of colonialism.

Conclusion

The population of Lower Myanmar around 1800 was estimated only one-quarter of the total population and sparsely populated area at the time of British annexation in 1852. Its population rose 2,747,148 in 1872 to 8,917,733 in 1941, an increase of 224.62 percent. The rate of population growth before the Second World War was 1.43 percent. The distribution of population is unevenly distributed and is determined by a number of basic geographic factors. Factors, contributing to the distribution of population density are many and varied. However, it has been analyzed that there is a high correlation between cropped land and population numbers. The population is dense in the fertile low lands and sparsely populated in

¹ *Census of India, 1931, Burma, Report*, p. 81.

mountainous and hilly region. During the colonial period, the male population was larger than the female. In the same year, the proportion of the working age increased and consequently, dependency ratio also dropped. The age and sex composition of Lower Myanmar population appears to have been largely structured by the age and sex distribution of the dominant immigrant group. As Myanmar is an agricultural country, the rural population is larger than those of the urban population.

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